

On-Demand Serverless Video Surveillance with Optimal Deployment of Deep Neural Networks

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We present an approach to optimally deploy Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) in serverless cloud architectures leveraging the latest advances of DNN optimization techniques for inference purposes along with tailored deployment strategies to help building cost-effective Video Surveillance System (VSS).

Despite the incredible benefits of serverless runtimes such as automatic elasticity, reduced cost, computing parallelization benefits, the serverless runtime has to deal with several limitations (stateless functions, lack of access of GPU, Additional latencies on function initialization, space constraints) (Ishakian et al., 2018).

Despite the cost fluctuation of the first three configurations (704MB to 1536MB) is being negligible, the price evolution of the remaining configurations is increased from 13.38% (2048MB) to 61%. (3008MB).

HOW TO DEAL WITH SUCH LIMITATIONS?

Although these strategies are available for general serverless architectures, the complexity of DNN models require a deep analysis. (Bianco et al., 2018)

Thus, we present a serverless architecture with tailored DNN optimization strategies to maximize inference efficiency.

The proposed VSS serverless architecture

The functionalities are decoupled in 3 layers:

- **Deep Learning layer (DL):** for DNN workloading and Computer Vision (CV) low-level algorithms.
- **High-Level Algorithm layer (HLA):** for Computer Vision complex pipelines supported by several DNN models.
- **Business Logic layer (BL):** utilities for I/O operations and communications.

The VSS serverless architecture is divided in two stages:

Cold Stage (Initialization process)
The serverless runtime container is initialized. Also, DNN models and libraries are downloaded and initialized (from step 1 to 8).

Warm stage (On-Demand Invocation task)
The handler instances are triggered from images coming from image source (from step 9 to 11). These images are stored in a Virtual Private Cloud. Supported by layers, the executed processed results are encoded to the preferred output.

The influence of the cold start delays according to local and global scope resource management strategies, reveals that global scope initialization performs best (2-4 secs difference).

LOCAL SCOPE

GLOBAL SCOPE

The influence of the allocated memory per function instance is very relevant especially between the 704MB and 1536MB configurations. The optimal way to achieve the maximum processing throughput is processing one image per each serverless function instance.

LATENCY EXPERIMENTS PER ALLOCATED MEMORY PER FUNCTION

The major bottleneck lies in the processing of each serverless function, while the influence of the memory allocation per function is visible in the processing speed.

References:

Bianco, S., Cadene, R., Celona, L., and Napoletano, P. (2018). Benchmark analysis of representative deep neural network architectures. *IEEE Access*, 6:64270–64277.

Ishakian, V., Muthusamy, V., and Slominski, A. (2018). Serving deep learning models in a serverless platform. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Cloud Engineering (IC2E)*, pages 257–262.

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